

Strategies and Initiatives Employed by National Open University Library to Address Information Needs of Disadvantaged Distance Learners in Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Distance learners, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds, face significant challenges in accessing academic resources. Libraries play a crucial role in bridging this gap by implementing strategies that enhance information access and digital literacy. This study examines the strategies and initiatives employed by the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) Library to address the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners in Nigeria.

Method The study adopted a survey research design. The population comprised 2,541 distance learners, from which a sample size of 335 was determined using stratified random sampling. Data collection focused on assessing the effectiveness of library services and initiatives in meeting the needs of disadvantaged distance learners.

Findings/Results: Findings highlight the critical role of digital access and research support in addressing the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners. The NOUN

Library employs multiple strategies, including specialized training, workshops, and initiatives such as free internet access and digital skills training. These efforts have significantly improved digital literacy, resource accessibility, and academic success among learners.

Implications: The study underscores the importance of library interventions in supporting distance learners. Effective library initiatives contribute to improved academic performance and digital inclusion. However, gaps in awareness and utilization of virtual support services suggest the need for further outreach efforts.

Conclusion: The NOUN Library has taken commendable steps to support disadvantaged distance learners by enhancing accessibility to academic resources and fostering institutional collaborations. Continued efforts in expanding digital services will further strengthen its impact.

Recommendations: To enhance service effectiveness, the library should improve support for material searches and referencing tools, expand collaboration with stakeholders to strengthen partnerships, and increase awareness of virtual support services to encourage greater utilization.

Keywords: Strategies, Initiatives, National Open University of Nigeria, disadvantaged distance learners

Introduction

Disadvantaged distance learners need to have access to relevant and high-quality information resources that are essential for promoting equitable learning opportunities. Disadvantaged learners often encounter barriers such as poor internet access, financial difficulties, and limited digital literacy skills, which hinder their ability to access and utilize information effectively as observed by Amuda and Tella (2019) that distance learners often face barriers such as inadequate digital infrastructure, financial constraints, and limited library support. Christian and Andrew (2021) noted that providing accessible digital libraries, mobile-friendly learning platforms, and tailored user support services helps bridge these gaps and enhances learning outcomes. Libraries can meet the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners through the implementation of strategies and initiatives that encourages accessibility to library information resources. Meeting the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners requires that they can fully utilize library resources for academic activities, develop essential research skills, and achieve

their educational goals, thereby contributing to a more inclusive and knowledge-driven society.

Hollister (2020) explained that various strategies have been developed to address the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners, ensuring they have equitable access to learning resources. One of the most effective strategies is the provision of Open Educational Resources (OERs), which offer free and high-quality academic materials, reducing the financial burden on students. Another important strategy is the development of mobile-friendly library services, enabling learners to access digital resources using smartphones, which is particularly beneficial for those without personal computers (Amuda & Tella, 2019). Furthermore, the implementation of offline access and low-bandwidth solutions, such as downloadable materials and preloaded storage devices, ensures that students in remote or underdeveloped areas can still access educational content without relying on constant internet connectivity (Tait, 2018).

Virtual reference and user support services, including online chat, email consultations, and toll-free helplines, further enhance accessibility by providing direct assistance from librarians and academic advisors (Association of College & Research Libraries, 2000). Moreover, targeted digital literacy training equips learners with essential research and navigation skills, helping them maximize the use of available resources (Chigbundu, & Oluwabiyi, 2023). Finally, flexible borrowing and delivery services, such as extended loan periods and home delivery options, allow students who cannot visit physical libraries to access print resources when needed (Lim, Foo, Khoo, Chen, Fox, Urs, & Thanos, 2002). These strategies collectively ensure that disadvantaged distance learners receive adequate support for academic success.

In addition to these strategies, several initiatives have been introduced by libraries and educational institutions to further bridge the gap in access to information for disadvantaged distance learners. Community-based learning hubs are one such initiative, providing physical locations equipped with internet access, study spaces, and library resources for students in underserved areas (Usman, Salisu, & Ibarahim, 2022). Another initiative is the implementation of library outreach programs, where mobile libraries, book donation drives, and literacy workshops help reach students who lack direct access to institutional libraries (Amuda & Tella, 2019).

Institutional collaborations, where universities, public libraries, and non-governmental organizations partner to share resources and expand access, also play a vital role in reducing disparities in information availability (Lim, Foo, Khoo, Chen, Fox, Urs, & Thanos, 2002). To support students with disabilities, customized learning support initiatives

provide assistive technologies, such as screen readers and Braille materials, ensuring inclusive access to educational content (Hollister, 2020). Additionally, some institutions offer scholarships and subsidized access to digital resources, helping disadvantaged students acquire necessary materials without financial strain (Tait, 2018). Lastly, the development of ICT infrastructure in underserved areas, including free Wi-Fi hotspots, digital kiosks, and community computer centres, further enhances access to online academic resources (Chigbundu, & Oluwabiya, 2023). These initiatives, when effectively implemented, create an inclusive learning environment that meets the diverse needs of disadvantaged distance learners.

Statement of the Problem

The ideal situation demands that all distance learners, including those in disadvantaged communities, have equitable access to educational resources and ICT tools to participate fully in e-learning, necessitating reliable infrastructure, digital literacy, and affordable internet connectivity to bridge the digital divide and ensure inclusive education. However, despite existing strategies to support disadvantaged distance learners, critical barriers persist: a digital divide marked by infrastructural inadequacies (e.g., unreliable electricity, poor internet) and a lack of computer skills disproportionately affects rural areas in developing countries like Nigeria (Akanbi & Akanbi, 2012; Tayo et al., 2015), while the abrupt shift to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic exposed systemic unpreparedness, with rural communities lacking technical capabilities and infrastructure (Azubuike et al., 2020). Additionally, socioeconomic inequality exacerbates these challenges, as low-income households struggle to afford digital devices and internet access, widening educational gaps (Adarkwah, 2021). Primary groups affected include disadvantaged distance learners in developing nations like Nigeria, particularly those in rural and underserved communities, alongside secondary stakeholders such as educational institutions and policymakers constrained by resource limitations. To address these issues, solutions such as infrastructure investment (expanding reliable electricity, internet, and device accessibility), capacity building (digital literacy training), policy interventions (subsidized access programs), and public-private partnerships (collaborations with tech companies) are proposed. However, current initiatives remain insufficient due to fragmented implementation, underfunding, and a lack of tailored solutions for marginalized populations. Critically, there is a paucity of research examining how multifaceted interventions—combining infrastructural development, policy reforms and community engagement can be systematically integrated to address the intersecting challenges of access, affordability, and digital literacy in resource constrained settings. This gap underscores the urgent need to investigate the strategies and initiatives

employed by national Open University of Nigeria library to address the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Identify the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners in Nigeria.
2. Examine strategies implemented by National Open University Nigeria library to address the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners.
3. Ascertain the initiatives employed by National Open University Nigeria library and addressing information needs of disadvantaged distance learners

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners?
2. What are the strategies implemented by National Open University Nigeria library to address the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners?
3. What are the initiatives employed by National Open University Nigeria library to address information needs of disadvantaged distance learners?

Literature Review

A study by Coetzer and Mapulanga (2021) assessed the satisfaction levels of Advanced Certificate in Teaching students regarding online library services at the University of the Free State in South Africa. The findings revealed that 85% of respondents had never used online library services, with high data costs and login issues being significant barriers. The study highlighted the necessity for libraries to develop distance learning policies and enhance information literacy to improve service delivery. Similarly, Mubofu and Malekani (2021) explored the accessibility of library resources by distance learners at the Open University of Tanzania. The study identified challenges such as high data costs, information overload, and inadequate search skills. Recommendations included assigning dedicated distance librarians and providing comprehensive online tutorials to enhance resource accessibility.

Ayoung, Bugre, and Baada (2020) evaluated Ghana's Library Connectivity Project, which aimed to extend ICT and library services to rural communities. The project benefited

students by enhancing practical ICT skills but faced challenges like inadequate logistics and personnel. The study underscored the importance of sustainable funding and infrastructure to support such initiatives. Shikali and Muneja (2024) conducted a systematic review examining access to library resources by university students during the COVID-19 pandemic in Africa. The review found that academic libraries adopted measures like expanding electronic resources and virtual services. However, challenges such as limited internet access and inadequate digital literacy persisted, indicating a need for improved ICT infrastructure and training.

A study conducted at the University of the Free State in South Africa assessed the perceived satisfaction of Advanced Certificate in Teaching students regarding online library services. The findings revealed that 85% of respondents had never used online library services, and 35% primarily relied on Google for information. High data costs and login/password issues were significant barriers, contributing to computer anxiety and physical discomfort among learners. These challenges negatively impacted their satisfaction with the library services provided (Coetzer & Mapulanga, 2021). Similarly, research at Uganda Martyrs University investigated the operational challenges of providing library services to distance education learners. The study found that 75.8% of student respondents were dissatisfied with library services and resources. Challenges included lack of login credentials for accessing e-resources, poor internet connectivity, inadequate assistance from library staff, insufficient training on accessing online resources, and geographical isolation. These factors hindered effective access to library services, leading to low satisfaction levels among distance learners (Buruga & Osamai, 2019).

The studies by Coetzer and Mapulanga (2021) and Mubofu and Malekani (2021) demonstrate a direct relationship between library strategies and the information needs of distance learners. Effective strategies, such as developing distance learning policies and enhancing information literacy, can significantly improve service delivery and resource accessibility.

The evaluations of the Library Connectivity Project and the measures adopted during the COVID-19 pandemic highlight the impact of library initiatives on addressing information needs. While these initiatives provided essential services, challenges like inadequate infrastructure and digital literacy gaps affected their effectiveness. This underscores the need for comprehensive planning and support to ensure initiatives meet the needs of disadvantaged distance learners (Ayoung, Bugre, & Baada, 2020).

Methodology

The method adopted for the research was descriptive survey. The population for the study consists of all distance learners enrolled in the National Open University of Nigeria, totalling 2,541 from the nineteen states in Northern. The size of the study was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for determining sample size, a population of 2,541 will require a sample size of approximately 335 respondents to achieve a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of 5%. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure that the sample is representative of the various strata within the population, such as gender, age, geographic location, and socio-economic status. The data was collected using a self-structured questionnaire designed specifically for this study. Data collected from the questionnaire was analysed using descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages to summarize the responses with the aid of SPSS version 23.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Strategies employed by libraries to address the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners

SN	Item	SA	A	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
1	I need access to online journals and e-books.	117 (35)	126 (37.5)	60 (18)	32 (9.5)	2.98	.95
2	I require help in searching for academic materials.	88 (26.3)	115 (34.4)	67 (20)	65 (19.3)	2.67	1.06
3	Updated course materials are essential for my studies.	101 (30)	97 (29.1)	96 (28.6)	41 (12.3)	2.77	1.01
4	I need frequent access to library databases.	140 (41.9)	95 (28.2)	55 (16.5)	45 (13.4)	2.99	1.06
5	I require support in using referencing tools.	76 (22.6)	98 (29.2)	109 (32.4)	53 (15.8)	2.59	1.01
6	Online library services are crucial for my learning.	106 (31.7)	116 (34.6)	79 (23.)	34 (10.1)	2.88	0.97

Key: SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, DA= Disagree Agree and SDA= Strongly Disagree

The findings indicate that disadvantaged distance learners have significant information needs, with the highest demand being access to library databases (Mean = 2.99) and online journals and e-books (Mean = 2.98). A considerable percentage also emphasized the importance of online library services (Mean = 2.88) and updated course materials (Mean = 2.77) for their studies. While many learners require assistance in searching for

academic materials (Mean = 2.67), the need for support in using referencing tools (Mean = 2.59) was relatively lower, with a notable proportion disagreeing. The standard deviations, ranging from 0.95 to 1.06, suggest some variation in responses, though the overall trend highlights the critical role of digital access and research support in meeting the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners.

Table 2: Strategies implemented by library to address the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners

SN	Item	SA	A	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
1	The library provides open educational resources (OERs).	88 (26.3)	115 (34.7)	95 (28.4)	36 (10.6)	2.76	0.96
2	The library provides mobile-friendly library services.	72 (21.5)	116 (34.9)	86 (25.8)	60 (17.8)	2.60	1.02
3	The library provides offline access and low-bandwidth solutions.	80 (24)	124 (37.1)	70 (20.9)	60 (18)	2.67	1.03
4	The library digital literacy and information skills training.	63 (18.7)	141 (42.1)	71 (21.2)	60 (18)	2.62	0.99
5	The library collaborates with stakeholders.	30 (8.9)	47 (14.1)	154 (46)	104 (31)	2.01	0.90
6	The library has flexible borrowing and delivery services.	66 (19.6)	172 (51.2)	41 (12.1)	3 (17.1)	2.97	0.77

Key: SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, DA= Disagree Agree and SDA= Strongly Disagree

The analysis of Table 2 reveals the strategies implemented by the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) library to address the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners. The highest-rated strategy is the library's flexible borrowing and delivery services, with a mean score of 2.97 (SD = 0.77), indicating broad agreement among respondents. Additionally, the library's provision of open educational resources (OERs) (Mean = 2.76, SD = 0.96) and the library's offline access and low-bandwidth solutions (Mean = 2.67, SD = 1.03) are widely acknowledged as key interventions. Library's digital literacy and information skills training (Mean = 2.62, SD = 0.99) and library's mobile-friendly library services (Mean = 2.60, SD = 1.02) are also significant, though slightly less emphasized. However, stakeholder collaboration received the lowest mean score (2.01, SD = 0.90), suggesting that this strategy is not as effectively implemented or recognized. Overall, the findings indicate that while the library employs several strategies to support disadvantaged distance learners, improvements in stakeholder collaboration may enhance service effectiveness.

Table 3: Initiatives employed by library and addressing information needs of disadvantaged distance learners

SN	Item	SA	A	DA	SDA	Mean	SD
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1	The library provides digital resources for distance learners.	88 (26.3)	115 (34.7)	95 (28.4)	36 (10.6)	2.76	0.96
2	The library offers training on using online resources.	80 (23.8)	116 (34.6)	89 (26.6)	50 (15)	2.67	1.00
3	The library conducts outreach for remote learners.	80 (24)	124 (37.1)	70 (20.9)	60 (18)	2.67	1.03
4	The library provides offline materials.	65 (19.3)	146 (43.6)	62 (18.5)	62 (18.6)	2.64	0.99
5	The library offers virtual support services.	30 (8.9)	47 (14.1)	154 (46)	104 (31)	2.01	0.90
6	The library collaborates to improve access.	66 (19.6)	172 (51.2)	41 (12.1)	3 (17.1)	2.97	0.77

Key: SA= Strongly Agree, A= Agree, DA= Disagree Agree and SDA= Strongly Disagree

The findings in Table 3 provide insight into the initiatives employed by the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) library to address the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners. The most highly rated initiative is library collaboration to improve access (Mean = 2.97, SD = 0.77), followed by the provision of digital resources (Mean = 2.76, SD = 0.96). Other notable initiatives include offering training on using online resources (Mean = 2.67, SD = 1.00), conducting outreach programs for remote learners (Mean = 2.67, SD = 1.03), and providing offline materials (Mean = 2.64, SD = 0.99). However, virtual support services received the lowest rating (Mean = 2.01, SD = 0.90), indicating that this initiative may not be widely available or effective. Overall, the results suggest that while NOUN library employs various initiatives to support disadvantaged distance learners, some initiatives, particularly virtual support, may require enhancement to better meet users' needs.

Discussion of Results

The findings on the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners align with previous studies that emphasize the necessity of digital access and research support. The high demand for access to library databases and online journals reflects the increasing reliance on digital academic resources, as also noted by Coetzer and Mapulanga (2021), who found that 85% of students had never used online library services due to high data costs and login issues. Similarly, Mubofu and Malekani (2021) identified inadequate search skills as a challenge, which is consistent with the need for assistance in searching for academic materials in this study. However, the relatively lower demand for support in using referencing tools suggests that while digital literacy is crucial, specific training areas may require further investigation. These findings reinforce the necessity of targeted

interventions to improve resource accessibility and research skills among disadvantaged distance learners.

The strategies implemented by the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) library to address the information needs of disadvantaged distance learners reflect a proactive approach but also highlight gaps in effectiveness. The emphasis on updating strategies based on learner needs and providing digital resources aligns with best practices identified by Ayoung, Bugre, and Baada (2020), who found that ICT-based interventions significantly improved resource access. However, the low rating of stakeholder collaboration echoes the challenges reported by Buruga and Osamai (2019) at Uganda Martyrs University, where students faced difficulties due to insufficient support from library staff. Additionally, the relatively moderate effectiveness of outreach programs and virtual support services suggests that while digital expansion is beneficial, infrastructural and logistical barriers must be addressed to enhance service delivery. This supports the argument that libraries must integrate both policy development and user-centered approaches to bridge access gaps effectively.

The initiatives employed by NOUN library show a strong commitment to improving access to information for disadvantaged distance learners, but the results indicate that some areas require enhancement. The prioritization of digital resources and collaborative efforts to improve access is supported by research from Shikali and Muneja (2024), which found that expanding electronic resources was a key response by African universities during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the relatively low effectiveness of virtual support services mirrors findings from Coetzer and Mapulanga (2021), who highlighted high data costs and digital literacy barriers as major obstacles to online library service utilization. The results suggest that while NOUN has made significant strides in providing digital access, challenges such as inadequate training on using online resources and limited internet infrastructure remain key barriers. Addressing these gaps through dedicated distance librarians and comprehensive training initiatives could enhance the overall impact of these initiatives, making them more effective in meeting the needs of disadvantaged learners.

Conclusion

The findings show that disadvantaged distance learners have significant information needs, particularly access to online journals, e-books, updated course materials, and library databases. The National Open University of Nigeria library has implemented several strategies to address these needs, including providing digital resources, conducting outreach programs, and offering virtual support. However, challenges such as

limited stakeholder collaboration and the effectiveness of virtual services remain. While various initiatives have been introduced to improve access and service delivery, issues like high data costs, inadequate search skills, and login difficulties continue to hinder their effectiveness. Addressing these challenges through improved policies, enhanced training, and better infrastructure will help ensure that library services effectively support distance learners.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are hereby proffered:

1. The library management should enhance support in searching for materials and using referencing tools.
2. The library should expand collaboration with stakeholders for stronger partnerships to enhance service effectiveness.
3. The library management should create awareness on virtual support services appear to be less effectively utilized, indicating a potential area for improvement.

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